

PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF FORMATION OF NATIONAL VALUES IN STUDENTS.

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Abstract. *The socio-psychological features of the formation of ethno-psychological characteristics of a person in family relations are considered in the article. The article also examines the socio-psychological characteristics of the role and essence of the family in the organization of the educational process. Another relevance of the article is that it reflects the environment in Western and Eastern families.*

Key words: *Family, values, ethnopsychologists, family relations, sociology, generation, education.*

ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ ЦЕННОСТЕЙ У СТУДЕНТОВ.

Аннотация. *В статье рассматриваются социально-психологические особенности формирования этнопсихологических характеристик личности в семейных отношениях. В статье также рассматриваются социально-психологические особенности роли и сущности семьи в организации воспитательного процесса. Другая актуальность статьи состоит в том, что она отражает среду в западных и восточных семьях.*

Ключевые слова: *Семья, ценности, этнопсихологи, семейные отношения, социология, поколение, образование.*

The family acts as a social space and a pedagogical and psychological factor that ensures the eternity of social life, the continuity of education, and influences how the next generation will grow up. A person is formed in the family. Family is a source of love, respect, solidarity and affection. Every developed society relies on these values. Family is sacred to me. The sanctity is that, first of all, if special attention is not paid to education in the family, environment in the family, honesty in the family, honesty in relation to education, no matter who he is, no matter where he works, there will never be results. Therefore, I pay great attention to the education of my children.

I have a special relationship with each of my children and grandchildren. - I know well the unique character of each of my grandchildren, I know their dreams, - says President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev. Everything that appears in a child's mind in a family environment remains for the rest of his life. A strong moral foundation in the family is the foundation of the society for educating a

mature person of tomorrow. In fact, living honestly, working, and raising children in family relations recognized for centuries, raised to the level of religious and moral values, is a way of social life and a source of development in Eastern education. gets genetic inheritance from parents, of course, he also has a share.

Biologists call this heredity. Enthusiasts who open their eyes to the world of light enjoy air, mother's milk and water, which were initially considered high material values. After that, the factor of family education begins, which is the basis of the realization of personal development and one of the important factors that ensure it. The family is the ground and tool that raises the "honor of the nation" to a high level.

Children are born in the family, unique characteristics and human qualities are formed, personality is formed. The scientific analysis of the problem of the influence of family culture and family relations on the formation and development of the ethnopsychological characteristics of the individual and the young generation is the subject of a number of scientific disciplines. In turn, the process of family relations is the first factor affecting human development, and a healthy environment in the family, both physically and mentally, has neither positive nor negative effects on the development of society and solving existing problems.

Based on the general axiological law of interaction between the individual and the society, our scientists defined the theoretical idea that the individual consists of a set of social relations.

From the same concept, it is natural to draw another theoretical conclusion that child rearing in the family has a social character. Cultural scientists analyze the influence of the culture of family relations on the education of the younger generation.

The division of family types according to demographic and social composition has its own characteristics and affects the culture of family relations. Most families in our country are complete families. A complete family is a family consisting of parents and children. This is a common family trait. Such families, in turn, are divided into patriarchal, nuclear, false unions. A unique feature of Uzbekistan is that the patriarchal way of life has been preserved in Uzbek families.

In this case, 2-3 generations of the household are common, and the family property, which is the basis of the economic unity of the family, is in the hands of the head of the family, and everyone is subordinate to him. Therefore, the relationship between the godfathers of related clans continues. Marriage of close relatives is also included.

Scientific research of the general cultural outlook of a person in family and family relations should begin with the expression of its development in accordance with the laws of social development. The development of the family is related to material production and the spiritual life of society. The connection between the change of family forms and the change of the spirituality

of material production at all historical stages since the time of primitive society has been widely analyzed in scientific literature. If we compare the characteristics of Eastern and Western families, the characteristics of European families are explained by the prevalence of free life without marriage, the increase in divorces and the decrease in birth rates. Some Western scholars have completely abolished marriage, saying that marriage restricts human freedom, which is contrary to human nature.

Of course, this is wrong and against human development. The second characteristic of modern families is their nuclear nature (Nuclear means "nucleus" in Latin. It consists of husband and children). Currently, under the influence of Western civilization, this type of family is increasing. In such families, the mother-in-law and daughter-in-law or daughters-in-law live separately, avoiding conflicts between them and having more valuable and loving cultural relations with each other in their lifestyle. This is a positive side of the issue and leads to the formation of a common cultural worldview of a person in family relations. Brides and grooms living separately from their parents learn to live independently, plan family life, and raise children independently.

Nuclear families have freedom in family matters, recreation and free time.

A third characteristic of modern families is the increase in discord ("mésalliance" is the French word for families in which there is a great difference between the social, cultural and economic status of the spouses). the increase of farmers, shepherds and representatives of different nationalities is a positive situation from the genetic and social point of view, as well as the preparation of the family and young people for the family. According to the famous philosopher, Freud, the family is built not only to live together, but also to live a full life and meet human needs.

A person's spirituality, upbringing, ethno-psychological characteristics, worldview mainly begin with the family. National values and national feelings are first instilled in our children through grandfather's upbringing, father's example, mother's love. An educated person who loves his family and respects his loved ones will never be against his country, he loves it, glorifies it, and fights for its future. First of all, national values, traditions of Uzbek family upbringing and their improvement, making our national values an integral part of our lifestyle, harmonizing Eastern culture and modern forms in mutual communication, educating our people. to achieve recognition as the basis of a prosperous life of people through the heritage of work. In the family, parents should monitor, control and advise the child on what kind of work he is doing, what books he is interested in, what movies he watches, what kind of music he is interested in, etc. Another aspect of our time that is not paid much attention, but requires attention, is the declining tradition of large families in Uzbek families.

If earlier children were closer to brothers and sisters, and the influence of ulama was significant in their education, now, mostly, parents remain close friends of one or two children. In this case, the literacy level of the parents should be taken into account. Within the framework of family relations, it is necessary to inculcate our national customs and traditions into our lives, to educate our children to love our values. First of all, if our parents understand the essence of the concept "The country begins at the threshold", how to instill a sense of national pride in the hearts of our children, how to decorate the face of our children's families, we think that it will be easier to work in educational institutions.

In the family, parents communicate directly and indirectly with their children and educate them meaningfully. It should be noted that the manners and skills of attentive and skillful listening can be acquired only by strengthening the knowledge of "skillful listening". Of course, there is a difference between parent and child during social life in the family. there will be events and incidents, misunderstandings. A person's purest feelings, first concepts and ideas are first formed in the family through the love and kind words of parents.

In the family environment, spiritual standards and views that determine the child's character and worldview are the foundation of such sacred concepts as goodness, nobility, kindness, and honor. It is recommended to follow the following socio-psychological, spiritual and educational criteria in the formation of national values and ethno-psychological characteristics in children growing up in the family:

- formation of children and reproductive culture, achieving rational organization of life;
- to study and widely promote the unique traditions and values of our people as the main factor for deciding on a healthy lifestyle in the family;
- increasing the responsibility, capacity and literacy of parents in the field of child education, increasing the pedagogical and psychological ability of parents, ensuring the unity of family and social education;
- educating the spiritually and physically mature generation in the family, in the family life of young people, preparing them for construction, arming them with modern business secrets;
- to achieve formation of national outlook in children in family relations.

The family has a huge and necessary social task. It is clear that raising a child is the most difficult social task. The personal and positive example of a father and mother is the key to the development of righteous and righteous children. The influence of the environment and society on the child is felt even after crossing the threshold to the outside world.

Educational institutions and their surrounding areas, in general, are the family social environment of a human child until the last moments of his life. Therefore, achieving the formation

of ethno-psychological and general characteristics of a person in family relations is important not only in personal life, but also in the socio-economic changes taking place in our country and their spiritual and moral improvement of the society.

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